

Direct and derivative spectrophotometric determination of cobalt with 5-bromosalicylaldehydethiosemicarbazone

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A simple and sensitive spectrophotometric method is developed for the determination of cobalt in aqueous DMF medium. The metal ion forms a brown coloured complex with 5-bromosalicylaldehydethiosemicarbazone (5-BSAT) in acidic medium. The complex shows absorption maximum at 410 nm. Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.29–5.89 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of cobalt(II). A method for the determination of cobalt by third derivative spectrophotometry is also proposed. The methods have been employed successfully for the determination of cobalt in steel samples.

A plethora of spectrophotometric methods for the determination of cobalt exist in literature. Some of the recently proposed methods using thiosemicarbazones¹ are found to be less sensitive. The methods employing different organic reagents have also been reported². Ishii *et al.*³ reported a second derivative spectrophotometric method for the determination of trace amounts of cobalt(II).

In the present paper, a simple, rapid, selective, sensitive and direct spectrophotometric method is reported for the determination of micro amounts of cobalt in aqueous DMF medium by complexing with 5-bromosalicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (5-BSAT).

The metal ion is determined spectrophotometrically both by zero order and third order derivative methods.

Results and discussion

The complex showed absorption maximum at 410 nm, where the reagent solution had negligible absorbance. Hence studies were conducted at 410 nm. The maximum and constant colour was obtained in the pH range 4.0–5.0 and the studies were carried out at pH 4.5.

A 15-fold molar excess of 5-BSAT was necessary for complete and constant colour development. Excess of the reagent has no effect on the absorbance of the complex. The complex dissolved completely in 15% aqueous DMF,

attaining maximum colouration. Hence further studies were carried out in 15% aqueous DMF. The colour reaction between Co^{II} and 5-BSAT was found instantaneous at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ and the colour remained stable for more than 72 h. The absorbance of the complex solution was found independent of the order of addition of the reactants. However, DMF should be added prior to the addition of the reagent to avoid its precipitation.

Beer's law was found to be obeyed in the concentration range 0.29–5.89 mg ml^{-1} of Co^{II} . The molar absorptivity of the complex at 410 nm and at pH 4.5 was $1.28 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the Sandell's sensitivity 0.0046 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. The standard deviation of the method for ten determinations of 2.35 μg of Co^{II} was ± 0.0017 .

The composition of the complex determined by using Job's and mole-ratio methods was found to be 1 : 2 (Co^{II} : 5-BSAT). The stability constant determined by Job's method was 2.15×10^9 .

The tolerance levels ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) of a foreign ions taken as the amount that caused an error in the absorbance by $\pm 2\%$ were as follows : Fe^{III} , 5641 (masked by phosphate), 280 (masked by citrate); phosphate, 2375; Pb^{II} , 1036; ascorbate, 870; tartrate, 740; Th^{IV} , 696; Ba^{II} , 686; iodide, 634; bromide, 600; DMF, 590; sulfate, 480; nitrate, 460; carbonate, 450; Al^{III} , 405; K^{I} , 390; thiourea, 380; citrate, 346; Mn^{II} , 275; chloride, 267; Ti^{IV} , 240; thiosulfate, 224; Ca^{II} , 200; W^{VI} , 184; oxalate, 176; fluoride, 142; Mg^{II} , 121; Ni^{II} , 120 (masked by citrate), 150 (masked by precipitated with DMG and filtered); Mo^{VI} , 95; Cu^{II} , 63 (masked by thiourea); U^{VI} , 24; Cr^{III} , 10; Zn^{II} and Ce^{IV} , 3; Ag^{I} , V^{V} and EDTA interfere. It can be seen that the large number of foreign ions do not interfere in the present method. However,

Fig. 1. Derivative spectra of Co^{II} -5-BSAT system : (a) first order, (b) second order, (c) third order, (d) fourth order, $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}]$, $\mu\text{g/ml}$: (1) 0.59; (2) 1.18; (3) 1.77.

larger amounts of Fe^{III} (1540-fold), Ni^{II} (40-fold) and Cu^{II} (30-fold) were masked with phosphate, citrate and thiourea, respectively. A small amount of Cr^{III} (10 μg) did not interfere.

Determination of Co^{II} by derivative spectrophotometry :

Derivative spectrophotometric methods have been developed for the determination of cobalt employing 5-BSAT in trace quantities. The first derivative spectrum shows maximum amplitude at 440 nm (Fig. 1). The second derivative curve shows maximum and zero amplitudes at 425 and 440 nm, respectively. The third derivative curve exhibits a zero amplitude at 460.2 nm and maximum at 475 nm for the fourth derivative spectrum, the maximum and zero point at 495 nm and 480.1 nm respectively. All the derivative amplitudes are found to be proportional to the concentration of Co^{II} . The plots between the derivative amplitude of the respective curves and concentration of Co^{II} are found to be linear in the range 0.20–4.30, 0.09–3.00, 0.06–2.40 and 0.12–2.92 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Co^{II} for 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th derivative curves, respectively. The statistical data of the linear plots indicate that the 3rd derivative spectrophotometric method is highly sensitive for the

determination of Co^{II} .

Application :

The proposed method was employed for the determination of Co^{II} in high speed steel, BCS 483 and JSS 607-6 steel samples and the results obtained were compared with the certified values. The results obtained in the direct spectrophotometric method show a relative error ± 0.7 to $\pm 1.10\%$. The third derivative method gave the results with an error of ± 0.9 to $\pm 1.3\%$.

The results of the present method were compared with those reported in literature employing thiosemicarbazones (Table 1). Most of the reported methods require rigid experimental conditions. The more sensitive methods involve extraction procedure. The present method is more sensitive and selective. The derivative method is well suitable for the determination of Co^{II} in microgram quantities in natural samples.

Experimental

A Shimadzu UV-160A spectrophotometer and a Philips PP 9046 pH meter were used. Suitable settings for derivative mode were as follows : spectral band width, 2

Table 1. Comparison with other methods

Reagent	λ_{\max} nm	ϵ^*	Interference/ Remarks	Ref.
2-Nitroso-1-naphthol	365	3.7	Extraction	4
	415	2.9	Extraction	4
Nitroso-R-salt	415	3.5	Heating the reaction mixture	4
3-Hydroxypicolinaldehyde- thiosemicarbazone	450	0.78	-	5
Phthaldehyde- thiosemicarbazone	385	0.56	-	6
Picolinaldehyde- thiosemicarbazone	410	0.74	-	7
Salicylaldehyde- thiosemicarbazone	400	1.1	Extraction	8
Picolinaldehyde-4-phenyl-3- thiosemicarbazone	390	2.99	Extraction	9
Acenaphthaquinone- thiosemicarbazone	410	0.48	-	10
Biacetylmonoxime- thiosemicarbazone	325	0.49	-	11
1,2-Cyclohexanedione- bisthiosemicarbazone	450	0.64	-	12
2,2'-Dihydroxybenzophenone- thiosemicarbazone	380	0.12	-	13
Furointhiosemicarbazone	365	0.81	Ni and Cu interfere. 30 ppm of Mn and Fe do not interfere in presence of fluoride	14
2-Hydroxyacetophenone- thiosemicarbazone	360	1.0	-	15
5-Bromosalicylaldehyde- thiosemicarbazone	410	1.28	-	Present method

*Molar absorptivity ($\times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

nm; wavelength readability, 0.1 nm increment; scan speed, fast (nearly 2400 nm min^{-1}); wavelength accuracy, $\pm 0.05 \text{ nm}$ automatic wavelength correction.

The reagent (5-bromosalicylaldehydethiosemicarbazone) was prepared by condensing 5-bromosalicylaldehyde and thiosemicarbazide as reported earlier¹⁶.

A 0.01 M solution in dimethylformamide was used.

Co^{II} solution was prepared by dissolving the requisite quantity of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (AnalaR) in double-distilled water, and standardized volumetrically using oxine¹⁷, working solutions were prepared diluting the stock solution. Buffer solutions were prepared by employing 1 M HCl and 1 M sodium acetate (pH 1–3), and 0.2 M sodium acetate and 0.2 acetic acid (pH 3.5–7.0). All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Procedure :

Direct spectrophotometry : In each of set of different 10 ml standard flasks, buffer solution (pH 4.5; 5 ml), various volumes (0.1–2.0 ml) of $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M Co}^{\text{II}}$ solution, DMF (1.5 ml) and 5-BSAT solution ($1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$; 1 ml) were taken and made up to the mark with double-distilled water. The absorbance was measured at 410 nm against the reagent blank. The calibration curve was prepared.

Derivative spectrophotometry : For the above solutions, the derivative spectra were recorded at 400–600 nm. The third derivative between 400 and 475 nm was measured by peak-peak method. The amplitude was plotted against the amount of cobalt to obtain the calibration curve.

The calibration graphs follow the straight line equation, $A = mC + b$, where C is the concentration of the solution, A the measured absorbance or derivative amplitude, and m and b are constants. By substituting the corresponding data into the above equation, calibration equations were obtained as $A = 0.212C + 0.002$ for the zero order data, and $A = 0.596C + 0.0002$ for the third derivative data.

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